

On the Mechanism of Unimolecular Reactions.

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The radiation theory of chemical reactions gives the number of activated molecules as follows:

$$N_a = N \int_{\nu_0}^{\infty} e^{-\frac{h\nu}{kT}} d\nu,$$

where N is the number of normal molecules and ν_0 is the threshold frequency. Thus the velocity coefficient assumes the form

$$k_1 = \frac{1}{N} \cdot \frac{dN}{dt} = \frac{N_a}{N} = \frac{kT}{h} \cdot e^{-\frac{h\nu_0}{kT}} \quad \dots (1).$$

Equation (1) resembles an equation due to Herzfeld (*Ann. phys.*, 1919, 57, 635). A continuous absorption band in the infra-red of the reactant should begin from this region, which is however not always the case. Moreover, all unimolecular reaction velocities are highly accelerated by external conditions, as they should be according to the above. Lindemann's collisional theory (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1922, 17, 598) has also been shown to be inadequate (Christiansen and Kramers, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1923, 104, 451). Further, the mechanism of the initial activation and parting off with the energy in the chain of reactions assumed by the 'chain theory' is not clear. In the present paper, the problem is dealt with in a different fashion.

In a previous paper (*Phil. Mag.*, 1931, vii, 12, 583 ; see also, *Z. Physik.*, 1930, 61, 411), two expressions for the velocity for unimolecular reactions have been deduced from the following considerations. In both cases, it is assumed that the normal molecules are activated by the absorption of infra-red radiation, and these activated molecules subsequently decompose, either in a manner similar to that involved in thermionic emissions, or by a process of

desorption. According to the first hypothesis, a statistical equilibrium between the 'free' active molecules and 'bound' active molecules is considered, and finally the following expression is obtained (*Phil. Mag., loc. cit.*) :

$$k_1 = \frac{2\pi \mu k^2}{h^3} \cdot T \cdot \frac{\beta_0}{B} \cdot e^{-\frac{Q_{AB}}{RT}}, \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where μ , the effective mass, equals $\frac{1}{m_A} + \frac{1}{m_B}$, m_A and m_B being

the masses of the resultants; β_v is the effective collisional area of recombination and $\beta_0 = T \cdot \beta_v$, B (or 'a') is the statistical weight factor. It may be noted that the critical increment Q_{AB} is composed of two factors, the radiant energy and the heat of dissociation Q_0 (corresponding to the ionisation potential in thermionic emission) and may also be expressed as $N \cdot h \cdot \nu_{AB}$, ν_{AB} is a virtual frequency,

given as the sum of ν_0 and ν_a $\left(= \frac{Q}{Nh} \right)$. This expression is

similar to that obtained by Roy (*Proc. Roy. Soc., 1926, A, 110, 543*) but differs by the factor 4, though derived from different considerations. Roy suggests a mechanism of photo-electric effect, and thereby claims the validity of the radiation hypothesis. It is possible that isolated instances exist where $Q=0$, and the reaction velocity depends solely on the infra-red frequency, in cases equation (1) may be valid and absorption band in the region of ν_0 should be obtained, as was found by Lewis in the case of inversion of sucrose. By introducing the values of the universal constants and taking logarithms of the expressions in equation (2), we have

$$\log_{10} k_1 = \log_{10} T + \log_{10} S - \frac{b}{T}, \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where $b = \frac{Q}{2.3 R}$ and $S = \frac{2\pi \mu k^2}{h^3} \cdot \frac{\beta}{a}$; b is calculated from the values of k_1 , at two temperatures. Substituting the average value of b and the corresponding value of k_1 and T in the above equation,

we obtain S . Again from the value of μ and S , we get the values of $\frac{\beta_0}{a}$ for different reactions. The values of $k_{1,cal.}$ and $k_{1,obs.}$ and

also of $\frac{\beta_0}{a}$ for different reactions are given in the following tables.

The real significance β_0 and a is not clear. Roy (*loc. cit.*) attributes to β_0 the value of the area of a circle, whose radius is the sum of the radii of the resultant products. This can be understood from the recent work of London (*Z. Physik.*, 1930, **63**, 245). If we assume this distance to depend on the pressure of the system at very low pressure, then the reaction velocity will be affected by the pressure under those circumstances, as has been experimentally observed by several authors (Rice and Ramsperger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **49**, 1617; Ramsperger, *ibid.*, 1917. **49**, 1495). The statistical factor, a , may be taken to be twice the number of bonds, as suggested by Roy.

TABLE I.

Decomposition of diethyl ether.

[Hinshelwood, *Proc. Roy Soc.*, 1927, **A**, 114, 84].

$$\log_{10} k_1 = 8.7578 + \log_{10} T - \frac{11512}{T}$$

T	obs.	kcal.
861	·0103	·0103
828.5	·00262	·00597
798	·000851	·0001697
49	·0000861	·00002447
699	·000000736	·000001356

$Q = 52480$ cal.
 $\beta_0/a = 4.671 \times 10^{-17}$
 (for the resultants $\text{C}_2\text{H}_6 + \text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}$)
 or $\beta_0/a = 1.069 \times 10^{-16}$
 (for the resultants $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4 + \text{CO} + \text{CH}_4$).

TABLE II.

Decomposition of dimethyl ether.

[Hinshelwood and Askey, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1927, **A**, 115, 215].

$$\log_{10} k_1 = 9.2980 + \log_{10} T - \frac{12103}{T}$$

T	$k_{obs.}$	kcal.
825	·00431	·00431
795	·00113	·00117
777	·000544	·000511
751	·000127	·0001391
725	·0000317	·0000362
695	·00000447	·000006459

$Q = 55170$ cal.
 $\beta_0/a = 3.414 \times 10^{-16}$ (for the
 resultants $\text{CH}_4 + \text{CO} + \text{H}_2$)
 or $\beta_0/a = 1.687 \times 10^{-15}$ (for the
 resultants $\text{CH}_4 + \text{CO} + \text{H}_2$).

TABLE III.

Decomposition of acetone.
[Hinshelwood and Hutchison,
Proc. Roy. Soc., 1926, **A**, 111,
245].

$$\log_{10} k_1 = 10.795 + \log_{10} T - \frac{13791}{T}.$$

T	$k_{\text{obs.}}$	$k_{\text{cal.}}$
904.5	.03677	.03172
890	.01670	.01756
857	.004346	.004346
809	.000462	.0004102
790	.0001557	.0001559
779	.00007254	.00008843

$$Q = 57860 \text{ cal.}$$

$$\beta_0/a = 6.275 \times 10^{-15}.$$

TABLE IV.

Decomposition of ethylene oxide.
[Winfield, Heckert and Mack,
J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1929, **51**,
2706].

$$\log_{10} k_1 = 11.547 + \log_{10} T - \frac{11134}{T}.$$

T	$k_{\text{obs.}} \times 10^2.$	$k_{\text{cal.}} \times 10^2.$
717.8	7.93	8.00
707.0	4.58	4.535
697.0	2.49	2.532
687.0	1.54	1.564
672.1	0.622	0.637
651.5	0.191	0.191

$$Q = 53720 \text{ cal.}$$

$$\beta_0/a = 7.868 \times 10^{-15}.$$

TABLE V.

Decomposition of $\text{CH}_3\text{N}_2\text{C}_3\text{H}_7$.
[Ramsperger, *J. Amer. Chem.*
Soc., 1929, **51**, 2134].

$$\log_{10} k_1 = 13.497 + \log_{10} T - \frac{10821}{T}.$$

T	$k_{\text{obs.}} \times 10^3.$	$k_{\text{cal.}} \times 10^3.$
533	0.09414	0.0544
543	0.1958	0.220
568	0.7142	0.714
573	2.372	1.69
595	11.80	6.9
605	25.05	9.8

$$Q = 45140 \text{ cal.}$$

(Q varies widely with temperature).

$$\frac{\beta_0}{a} = 2.425 \times 10^{-15}.$$

TABLE VI.

*Decomposition of diazobenzene
chloride.* [Cain and Nicoll, *J. Chem.*
Soc., 1903, **83**, 470].

$$\log_{10} k_1 = 11.475 + \log_{10} T - \frac{5008}{T}.$$

T	$k_{\text{obs.}} \times 10^3.$	$k_{\text{cal.}} \times 10^3.$
293	0.72	0.7101
303	2.95	2.669
313	8.87	9.133
323	29.8	29.81
333	109.3	90.63

$$Q = 22830 \text{ cal.}$$

$$\frac{\beta_0}{a} = 3.221 \times 10^{-14}.$$

TABLE X.

Decomposition of nitrous oxide at different pressures. [Nagasako and Volmer, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **B,10**, 414; cf. Hinshelwood, *ibid.*, 1930, **B,10**, 157].

$$\log_{10}k_1 = 7.5374 + \log_{10}T - \frac{11183}{T}. \quad \log_{10}k_1 = 7.3501 + \log_{10}T - \frac{10666}{T}.$$

T	Pressure = 1000 mm.		Pressure = 8000 mm.	
	$k_{\text{obs.}} \times 10^2.$	$k_{\text{cal.}} \times 10^2.$	$k_{\text{obs.}} \times 10^2.$	$k_{\text{cal.}} \times 10^2.$
938	4.3	3.887	9.6	9.6
925	3.2	2.591	2.4	2.996
893	1.0	0.9517	1.6	1.358
877	0.62	0.620	0.48	0.4995

TABLE XI.

Decomposition of propionic aldehyde. [Hinshelwood and Thomson, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1927, **A,113**, 221].

$$\log_{10}k_1 = 9.2075 + \log_{10}T - \frac{11810}{T}.$$

T	$k_{\text{obs.}} \times 10^3.$	$k_{\text{cal.}} \times 10^3.$
877	39.4	49.03
849	15.6	17.24
822	5.67	5.92
796	1.35	1.898
765	0.45	0.458
722	0.052	0.052

$$Q = 5500 \text{ cal.} \quad \beta_0/\alpha = 1.022 \times 10^{-16}.$$

TABLE XII.

Decomposition of azomethane. [Ramspersger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **49**, 912].

$$\log_{10}k_1 = 12.9896 + \log_{10}T - \frac{11085}{T}.$$

T	$k_{\text{obs.}} \times 10^3.$	$k_{\text{cal.}} \times 10^3.$
551.6	.05	.0448
560.3	.10	.095
571.2	.252	.227
578.3	.457	.400
586.7	.747	.755
600.4	2.08	2.08

$$Q = 50510 \text{ cal.} \quad \beta_0/\alpha = 1.027 \times 10^{-12}.$$

TABLE XIII.

Decomposition of nitryl chloride.
 [Schumacher and Sprenger, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, **B**, 12, 123].

$$\log_{10}k_1 = 10.796 + \log_{10}T - \frac{5957}{T}.$$

T	$k_{\text{obs.}} \times 10^3.$	$k_{\text{cal.}} \times 10^3.$
373	2.63	2.943
403	34.8	34.8
418	82.2	80.0
423	95.2	174.8

$$Q = 274000 \text{ cal.} \quad \beta_0/\alpha = 4.551 \times 10^{-15}.$$

TABLE XIV.

Decomposition of azoisopropane.
 [Ramsperger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **50**, 714].

$$\log_{10}k_1 = 11.0171 - \log_{10}T - \frac{8926}{T}.$$

T	$k_{\text{obs.}} \times 10^3.$	$k_{\text{cal.}} \times 10^3.$
523	0.461	0.461
533	1.03	0.986
543	2.01	2.05
553	3.88	4.167
563	7.96	8.033

$$Q = 406000 \text{ cal.} \quad \beta_0/\alpha = 7.196 \times 10^{-15}.$$

TABLE XV.

Racemisation of pinene.

[Smith, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **49**, 43].

$$\log_{10}k_1 = 12.9219 + \log_{10}T - \frac{9262}{T}.$$

T	$k_{\text{obs.}} \times 10^5.$	$k_{\text{cal.}} \times 10^5.$
457.	2.20	2.20
471.0	8.57	8.412
490.9	58.0	55.33
503.9	169.0	175.6
510.4	307.0	389.0

$$Q = 42220 \text{ cal.}$$

$$\beta_0/\alpha = 8.956 \times 10^{-14}.$$

TABLE XVI_B

Reaction.	$\beta_0/\alpha.$	No. of bonds.	$\alpha.$	$\beta_0.$
$\begin{array}{l} \text{OH}_3 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{O} \end{array} \rightarrow \text{CH}_4 + \text{COH}_2$	3.414×10^{-16}	HCH=	4	1.36×10^{-15}
$\begin{array}{l} \text{CH}_3 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{O} \end{array} \rightarrow \text{CH}_4 + \text{CO} + \text{H}_2$	1.687×10^{-15}	$\equiv \text{CO}-$	8	1.5×10^{-14}
$\begin{array}{l} \text{C}_2\text{H}_5 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{O} \end{array} \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{H}_6 + \text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}$	4.671×10^{-17}	$\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{CHO} =$	4	1.8×10^{-16}
$\begin{array}{l} \text{C}_2\text{H}_5 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{O} \end{array} \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{H}_6 + \text{CO} + \text{CH}_4$	1.069×10^{-16}	$\equiv \text{CO}-$	8	8.55×10^{-14}
$\begin{array}{l} \text{CH}_3 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{CO} \end{array} \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{H}_6 + \text{CO}$	6.273×10^{-15}	$\equiv \text{CO}-$	8	4.9×10^{-14}
$\begin{array}{l} \text{CH}_3 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{O} \end{array} \rightarrow \text{CH}_4 + \text{CO}$	7.869×10^{-14}	$\equiv \text{CO}-$	8	6.2×10^{-13}
$\begin{array}{l} \text{CH}_2 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{O} \end{array} \rightarrow \text{CH}_4 + \text{CO}$	7.869×10^{-14}	$\equiv \text{CO}-$	8	6.2×10^{-13}
$\begin{array}{l} \text{C}_3\text{H}_7 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{N}_2 \end{array} \rightarrow \text{C}_4\text{H}_{10} + \text{N}_2$	2.425×10^{-13}	$-\text{N} : \text{N}-$	4	9.7×10^{-13}
$\begin{array}{l} \text{CH}_3 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{N}_2 \end{array} \rightarrow \text{C}_6\text{H}_{14} + \text{N}_2$	7.196×10^{-15}	,,	4	2.8×10^{-14}
$\begin{array}{l} \text{C}_3\text{H}_7 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{N}_2 \end{array} \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{H}_6 + \text{N}_2$	1.027×10^{-12}	,,	4	4.1×10^{-12}
$\begin{array}{l} \text{CH}_3 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{N}_2 \end{array} \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{H}_6 + \text{N}_2$	1.027×10^{-12}	,,	4	4.1×10^{-12}
$\begin{array}{l} \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{N}_2 \end{array} \rightarrow \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{OH} + \text{N}_2 + \text{HCl}$	3.221×10^{-14}	,,	4	1.28×10^{-13}
$\begin{array}{l} \text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{N}_2 \end{array} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OH} + \text{N}_2 + \text{HCl}$	1.687×10^{-12}	,,	,,	6.7×10^{-12}
(o) $\begin{array}{l} \text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{Cl} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{N}_2 \end{array} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{Cl} + \text{N}_2$	1.666×10^{-13}	,,	,,	6.6×10^{-13}
(p) $\begin{array}{l} \text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{Cl} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{N}_2 \end{array} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{Cl} + \text{N}_2$	4.837×10^{-14}	,,	,,	1.93×10^{-13}
(m) $\text{N}_2\text{O}_5 \rightarrow \text{N}_2\text{O}_4 + \text{O}$	7.36×10^{-15}	$=\text{O}$	4	2.9×10^{-14}
$\text{PH}_3 \rightarrow \text{P} + 3\text{H}$	16.0×10^{-15}	$\equiv \text{P}$	6	6.4×10^{-14}
$\text{NO}_2\text{Cl} \rightarrow \text{NO}_2 + \text{Cl}$	4.551×10^{-15}	$\text{Cl} =$	4	9.1×10^{-15}
$\begin{array}{l} \text{COOEt} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{CO} \cdot \text{CHOEt} \end{array} \rightarrow \text{CO} + \text{COOEt} + \text{CHOEt}$	5.4×10^{-14}	$\equiv \text{C}-\text{O}-$	8	4.3×10^{-13}
$\text{CCl}_3 \cdot \text{COOH} \rightarrow \text{CHCl}_3 \cdot \text{CO}_2$	1.780×10^{-10}	$-\text{C} \begin{array}{l} \diagup \text{O} \\ \diagdown \text{O} \end{array}$	4	7.1×10^{-10}
$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16} \rightarrow \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}$ (Pinene) (Dipentein)	8.956×10^{-14}			
$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{15}\text{O} \cdot \text{COOH} \rightarrow \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{O} + \text{CO}_2$ (In water)	2.606×10^{-14}	$-\text{C} \begin{array}{l} \diagup \text{O} \\ \diagdown \text{O} \end{array}$	4	1.04×10^{-13}
„ „ (In benzene)	1.544×10^{-15}	,	4	6.1×10^{-15}

In connection with the second method of procedure mentioned above, it may be pointed out that adsorption plays an important role in catalysed or "wall reactions", in which the critical increment is really the sum of the adsorption potential (heat of adsorption) and the heat of activation (Taylor, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 578). In the present case, it is assumed that the chemically active molecules are held bound within the molecular system in the adsorbed state, and the rate of reaction is identified with the rate of 'desorption'.

By using the value of the Langmuir constant in the equation of adsorption (Kar and Ganguli, *Phys. Z.*, 1929, 30, 918), the following expression for the velocity coefficient is obtained (*cf. Phil. Mag, loc. cit.*):

$$k_a = \frac{kT}{\rho} \cdot e^{-\frac{Q_{AB}}{RT}},$$

where $\rho = nh$ and Q_{AB} is composed of the radiant energy $Nh\nu_0$ and the heat of adsorption. For $\nu = 1$, the expression becomes identical with that of Herzfeld (*loc. cit.*). Now if ν is the average vibrational frequency of the molecules, we have $h\nu = RT$ for ordinary temperature (Ganguli, *Z. Phys.*, 1930, 64, 81) and hence

$$k_1 = \frac{\nu}{n} \cdot e^{-\frac{h\nu_{AB}}{kT}};$$

(*cf. Dushman and Christiansen's expressions*).

Taking into account the number of molecules escaping in all directions, we have (*cf. Polanyi and Winger, Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 139, 432),

$$k_1 = \frac{2Q}{nNh} \cdot e^{-\frac{Q}{RT}} = \frac{2\nu_{AB}}{n} \cdot e^{-\frac{h\nu_{AB}}{kT}} \dots (4).$$

For the unimolecular adsorption layer ($n=1$) (Kar and Ganguli, *loc. cit.*), equation (2) becomes identified with Polanyi's expression (*loc. cit.*), while for bimolecular adsorption layer ($n=2$), we have the Dushman's expression.

Equation (4) may be obtained in a much simpler manner. If ν is the frequency of vibration and if the rate of reaction depends on the collision of vibrating molecules (the vibrational energy, $h\nu$ corresponding to the critical increment), the number of active molecules colliding per second (Rodebush, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 606) is given by

$$dN = 2\nu\bar{N},$$

where \bar{N} is the number of active molecules. Now as $h\nu$ is the energy of activation,

$$\bar{N} = Ne^{-h\nu/kT} \text{ and hence}$$

$$k_1 = \frac{dN}{N} = 2\nu e^{-\frac{h\nu}{kT}}$$

Expressing k_1 in the form due to Arrhenius, $k_1 = Be^{-\frac{Q}{RT}}$, the observed values of B are compared with the calculated values, $B = \frac{RT}{h}$ or $B = \nu$ or 2ν for various reactions, and entered in Table XVII.

TABLE XVII.

Reaction equation.	Q.	log ₁₀ B.	log ₁₀ ν.	$\frac{kT}{h}$.	Author.
$C_3H_7N_2C_3H_7 = C_6H_{14} + N_2$	40900	13.6	14.52	13.0	Ramsperger (<i>J. Amer. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1928, 60, 714).
$C_3H_7N_2CH_3 = C_4H_{10} + N_2$	47500	15.3	14.59	13.28 (T=600)	" (<i>loc. cit.</i>).
$CH_3N_2CH_3 = C_2H_6 + N_2$	51200	16.0	14.62	---	" (<i>ibid.</i> , 1927, 49, 912, 1495).
$CH_3OCH_3 \rightarrow [CH_4 + COH_2]$ \downarrow $\rightarrow CH_4 + CO + H_2$	58500	13.06	14.68	13.34 (T=700)	Hinschelwood and Askey (<i>loc. cit.</i>).
$C_2H_5OO_2H_5 \rightarrow [C_2H_6 + C_2H_4O]$ \downarrow $\rightarrow C_2H_6 + CO + CH_4$	53000	11.50	14.64	13.34 (T=700)	Hinschelwood (<i>loc. cit.</i>).
$CH_6COCH_3 \rightarrow CO + C_2H_6$	68500	15.20	14.75	13.457 (T=900)	Hinschelwood and Hutchinson (<i>loc. cit.</i>).
$CH_3CH_2COH \rightarrow C_2H_6 + CO$	54000	12.00	15.20	13.34 (T=700)	Hinschelwood and Thompson (<i>loc. cit.</i>).
$CH_2OCH_2 \rightarrow CO + CH_4$	52000	14.70	14.63	13.34 (T=700)	Winfield, Heckart and Mack (<i>loc. cit.</i>).
$(CH_3)_2CH \cdot CH_2Br \rightarrow (CH_2)_3C \cdot Br$	6000	1.5	13.67		Dienger (<i>Z. Phys. Chem.</i> , 1928, 136, 93).
$C_{10}H_{16} \rightarrow$ Dipentene	43700	14.3	14.57	13.0 (T=325)	Smith (<i>J. Amer. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1927, 49, 43).
$N_2O_5 \rightarrow [N_2O_3 + O_2] \rightarrow N_2O_4 + \frac{1}{2}O_2$	24800	13.8	14.30	13.0 (T=325)	Daniels and Johnston (<i>J. Amer. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1921, 43, 53).
$NO_2Cl \rightarrow NO_2 + Cl$ $\rightarrow 2NO_2Cl = 2NO + Cl_2$	28000	13.0	14.34	13.04 (T=370)	Schumscher and Sprenger (<i>Z. Elektrochem.</i> , 1929, 35, 653).

Reaction equation.	Q.	log ₁₀ B.	log ₁₀ v.	$\frac{kT}{h}$.	Author.
4 $C_{11}H_{16}O_3 \longrightarrow C_{10}H_{16}O + CO_2$ (in water)	29700	13.1	14.38	13.04 (T=370)	Bredig and Balcom (<i>loc. cit.</i>).
$C_{11}H_{16}O_3 \longrightarrow C_{10}H_{16}O + CO_2$ (in benzene)	27800	12.6	14.34	13.04 (T=370)	" "
" " (in acetophenone)	29000	13.2	14.34	13.04 (T=370)	" "
" " (in aniline)	22500	10.0	14.25	13.04 (T=370)	" "
$CO(NH_2)_2 \longrightarrow NH_4OCN$ (in water)	32100	14.4	14.4		Fawcitt and Burrow (<i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1914, 106, 615).
" " (in 10 p.c. alcohol)	32300	14.5	14.45		" "
" " (in 80 p.c. alcohol)	80400	13.0	14.39		" "
Disociation of $CH_3 \cdot C_2H_5 \cdot C_6H_5 \cdot CH_2 \cdot NBr$ (in chloroform)	30000	16.7	14.38		Christiansen and Kramers (<i>loc. cit.</i>).
" " (in bromoform)	27700	15.2	14.36		" "
" " (in tetrachlorethane)	24300	13.3	14.30		" "
Disociation of $(C_2H_5)_3SBr$	31100	16.4	14.44		v. Halban (<i>Z. Phys. Chem.</i> , 1909, 67, 129; 1911, 77, 719).
" " (in tetrachloroethane)	29300	13.3	14.38		" "
" " (in acetic acid)	33300	17.8	14.31		" "
" " (in amyl alcohol)	25100	14.6	14.77		" "
" " (in 90 p.c. H_2SO_4)	48000	14.00	14.30	13.44 (T=300)	Cain and Nicoll (<i>loc. cit.</i>).
$HCOOH \longrightarrow H_2O$ (in 90 p.c. H_2SO_4)	48000	14.00			Trautz and Bhandarkar (<i>Z. anorg. Chem.</i> , 1919, 106, 95).

The above conclusions are based on the consideration that unimolecular reactions are brought about by radiation followed by collision, both in the case of decomposition, resembling thermionic emission as well as 'desorption'. In most cases, neither radiation nor collision is alone sufficient to bring about the reactions, although there are isolated instances (cited above), in which the heat of reaction (critical increment) is derived entirely from infra-red radiation. That infra-red frequency is absorbed by the molecules has been recently demonstrated by the beautiful work of C. V. Raman (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1928, 2, 287) on anomalous scattering. In fact, Raman effect may be represented according to the following scheme of the general mechanism of transformation of chemical reactants proposed by Perrin (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1922, 17, 546):

$$w + \sum h\nu + A = A' + \sum h\nu' + w'.$$

The difference between the Raman effect and ordinary chemical reaction is that in the first case that molecules remain in the activated state and do not subsequently decompose, as in the latter. We may however consider Raman effect as a unimolecular chemical reaction and apply the above methods for determining the number of excited molecules. Recently the present author has applied a method originating from Christiansen (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, *loc. cit.*) for determining the number of activated molecules, and has thus obtained expressions for the intensities of the Stokes and anti-Stokes lines (Communicated to *Phil. Mag.*), which agree with the results of other standard authors. Another point may be mentioned in this connection. One of the objections raised against the radiation hypothesis is that the small density of the active radiation energy is unable to furnish the total energy required to bring about the reaction. Now according to the Raman effect, even if the incident radiation do not correspond to the active frequency, this may be resolved, such that the molecules absorb the infra-red frequency ν_i , and the scattered radiation will be modified (the frequency being $\nu - \nu_i$). Hence, since any frequency of radiation may be scattered by the molecules, which however can retain the characteristic infra-red frequency, there can be no question as regards the deficiency of density of the activating radiation.

Summary.

The absorption of radiation for initial activation is to be associated with the rise in the energy level for vibration and rotation. This may cause the loosening of the valency electrons or widespread separation of the constituents as in dissociation. In most cases however, as has been pointed out, radiation alone is not sufficient; it supplies energy corresponding to the resonance potential. The loosely bound electrons separate, (causing disruption of molecules), only by subsequent collision of the active molecules with the normal molecules. The total energy thus supplied corresponds to the ionisation potential, in the case of ionisation of elementary substances. Only in few cases, radiation alone is effective in bringing about the rupture of molecules; these reactions thus resemble those photochemical reactions which obey Einstein's law. In general however, the energy required for bringing about thermal unimolecular reactions is derived partly from radiation and partly from collision and the same argument may possibly be advanced for photochemical reactions as well.

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